

ANALYSIS OF MODERN CHANGES IN THE CINEMA

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Annotation. The article explores the concept of national cinema, its content and issues related to changes in the field.

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In the late 20th and early 21st centuries, the crisis of the modern value system was clearly manifested. It can be characterized by a crisis of philosophy, aesthetics, art, human views. Currently, the concept of postmodernism, which reigned at the end of the last century, is losing ground and an urgent issue appears on the agenda. The term "art" is usually used in at least two senses. In one case, it simply means skill, for example, when talking about the art of making dishes from clay or the art of sewing clothes. In this sense, no one questions the legitimacy of the phrase "The Art of cinema"; too much skill can be spent even in creating the dumbest film. However, the word "art" has a different meaning, such as when talking about music or the art of poetry, and when calling for Shakespeare's "King Lear" or Beethoven's "Ninth Symphony". In such cases, it means more than technical skill, and before we conclude, it is recommended to solve the question of how legitimate it is to consider cinema as art in this sense.

The emergence and development of cinema, a new type of art, is associated with the development of science, technology, as well as the achievements of the pre-existing types of art. The emergence of cinema was also caused by a number of discoveries. In the late 19th century, electricity entered the marriage of people, the science of chemistry developed, it played a large role in the emergence of photography (photography), and later in the invention of film (1887). J. for the upcoming film. An apparatus with moving pictures invented by Plato, Edison's apparatus for transmitting motion to the film, became important. At the same time, experiments were carried out on the creation of a projective apparatus as well. In several countries (USA, Germany, France, Russia), research was carried out on the discovery of cinema, aimed at a specific goal, and the main technical discoveries were made: shooting and rendering (syomka and projection) apparatus were created, a special kinoplyonka was developed. From the same things, the inventor brother L. and O. The Lumières (28 December 1895) used it in Paris to film and screen the early films "the arrival of the train", "wet sucker to the jaw", "feeding the child". This day is considered the day of the emergence of cinema. Traditional arts also had a significant impact on the formation of cinema as an art form. In ancient

times, paintings, miniatures, which the peoples of the world drew on the rocks, and in the XVIII and XIX centuries, the development of graphics, painting and, finally, the emergence of photography — all this became complete with the search for ways to combine space and time, movement and time. In a detailed study of each type of art, we see an effort to solve these important tasks. For example, the composition of any Oriental miniature consists of a complex consistent harmonization of the movement taking place in it, indicating that their authors sought to reflect time in their works. In the work of many artists (Domye: "Don Quixote and Sancho Panso", pictures taken by the famous French photographer Paul Nodar) one can see in modern language the emergence of "seriality", in which one seeks to fully show, embody the process of time and movement. World artists sought such means of expression in their art that, as a result, they managed to show the movement in the paintings in which they worked, in incredibly diverse layouts and rakurs. The relentless search for the way to show the dynamics of movement in time and space through Fine Arts was made by artists P. Breugel, I. It is observed in the works of Repin as well as Impressionists.

Consequently, even young cinema could not be indifferent to these studies, it took advantage of the results of these studies in its development. During the silent era of cinema, its proximity to the visual arts is especially evident. Accordingly, it is not for nothing that many film theorists consider cinema to belong to the Fine Arts. For example, the great filmmaker S. M. Eisenstein believes that the history of cinema is part of the history of painting. Cinema took shape in homage, who mastered the experience of all the arts before him. It sought to obtain from each of these arts characteristics that would help develop its own means of expression. In the period when Uzbek artistic cinema was taking shape (in 1927), Fitrat wrote in his article "the source (origin) of art" that "cinema, like theater, came from six wonderful arts: dance, music, literature, painting, sculpture, architecture: or in other words: cinema is an effective fruit of six ancient wonderful arts". A little later Cinema acquired a certain experience, this experience made it possible to make theoretical generalizations and wrote many works about cinema S. M. Eisenstein also concluded that "the roots of each element in cinema lie in other arts," because the theory of the spontaneous generation of cinema has already lived its own life," it is necessary to look for the properties of cinema from close to each other types of art".

The fact that cinema absorbed experiences from Arts close to each other at the stage of its formation allowed it to become truly artistic in a short time, standing in the same line as traditional arts. As cinema develops, its relationship with the

system of artistic culture in a particular country becomes more complex, deepening and acquiring the features of creative communication, mutual assistance. Genres of cinema types were formed under the influence of fiction. In the early days of cinema, literary genres shifted to feature films, and directors strictly followed their laws. However, as cinema developed, the boundaries of the genre expanded. Genre intervention takes place in fictional cinema to reveal the idea, theme, purpose of the film, the character of the characters in depth. This phenomenon is also characteristic of modern cinema. Famous Russian director E. Let's remember Ryazanov's film "avoid the car". It can be included in the comedy genre, but at the same time it manifests itself as a detective. The means of expression of one genre or another move together, but they become the only work with the unity of intention and character of the hero. The richness of genres of all types of cinema is due to the fact that cinematographers master new-new topics, plots, life materials. The genre that the filmmaker chooses for his script and the film clearly expresses both the artist's attitude towards the material and his style and interpretation. In the genre, his worldview, artistic thinking are manifested. The fact that the screenwriter, the director chooses a particular genre for his work, that it develops in a certain way the material on which this film is based on drama, is to determine the artistic dimension of this work. Thus, the genre determines the choice of the means of expression necessary for the director to realize his intention. Genre selection is one of the responsible aspects in the work of both the screenwriter and the director. The famous scientist who studied the morphology and genres of fairy tales V. Y. Progsch said, "The belonging of a work to a genre is not a superficial feature, but a quality that defines the whole artistic fabric of the work".

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